

Marketing tools as an element of innovative development and demand generation in conditions of uncertainty

The subject of the research is a theoretical and methodological analysis of basic marketing tools that will help in innovative development and demand generation for companies under conditions of uncertainty.

The aim of the research is to determine the essence, main advantages and features of the use of marketing tools in the context of innovative development, demand generation and uncertainty.

Research methods. The article uses general research methods, as well as special economic methods, methods of abstraction, induction, analysis and synthesis, grouping, classification, graphical and tabular methods.

Results of the investigation. It has been established that in the context of rapid changes in the economic environment and globalization, market competition is becoming increasingly intense. It is determined that marketing tools play a key role in generating demand, as they allow for more accurate monitoring of market changes, forecasting consumer behavior and adapting offers to their new needs. It is proved that in the face of uncertainty and changes in consumer preferences, tools such as digital marketing, social media, content marketing and personalization of offers are becoming important, allowing effectively communicating with the target audience and responding to its needs in real time. The article analyzes innovative approaches to marketing that help enterprises not only attract new consumers but also create brand loyalty, which is an important aspect of successful development in the face of unpredictable changes in the market. The author proposes a definition of marketing tools as methods, tools and technologies used to analyze the market, identify consumer needs, promote products and build long-term relationships with customers, covering a wide range of areas (from classic tools such as advertising and direct marketing to modern digital technologies such as social media, data analytics and marketing automation).

Scope of the results. Marketing, communication marketing, management, advertising, risk management, economics.

Conclusions. It has been established that the main marketing tools are dynamic combinations of platforms and services (including social media, email marketing, SEO), which are called modern digital marketing. The following basic marketing tools have been identified: Ranktracker, Sendinblue, HubSpot, Statusbrew, Google Analytics, WordPress, Slack, BuzzStream, Basecamp, Filmora, which are an element of innovative development and demand generation in conditions of uncertainty and can improve the implementation of marketing strategies of various companies in social networks. It is proved that with the help of these tools it is possible to automate many processes and optimize marketing campaigns, which will lead to their further innovative development and competitiveness, as well as the formation and increase of demand for companies' products under conditions of uncertainty and risk.

Keywords: marketing tools, demand generation, innovative development, conditions of uncertainty, Ranktracker, Sendinblue, HubSpot, Statusbrew, Google Analytics, WordPress, Slack, BuzzStream, Basecamp, Filmora, management, companies.

Маркетингові інструменти як елемент інноваційного розвитку та формування попиту в умовах невизначеності

Предметом дослідження є теоретико–методичний аналіз базових маркетингових інструментів, що допоможуть в інноваційному розвитку та формуванні попиту компаніям в умовах невизначеності.

Метою дослідження є визначення сутності, основних переваг та особливостей використання маркетингових інструментів в контексті інноваційного розвитку, формування попиту та умовах невизначеності.

Методи дослідження. В статті було використано загальні методи дослідження, а також спеціальні економічні, методи абстракції, індукції, аналізу та синтезу, групування, класифікації, графічний та табличний методи.

Результати роботи. Встановлено, що в умовах швидких змін економічного середовища та глобалізації конкуренція на ринку стає все більш інтенсивною. Визначено, що маркетингові інструменти відіграють ключову роль у формуванні попиту, оскільки дозволяють здійснювати точніший моніторинг змін на ринку, прогнозувати поведінку споживачів та адаптувати пропозиції до їхніх нових потреб. Доведено, що в умовах невизначеності та змін у споживчих уподобаннях важливими стають такі інструменти, як цифровий маркетинг, соціальні мережі, контент–маркетинг та персоналізація пропозицій, що дозволяють ефективно комунікувати з цільовою аудиторією та реагувати на її потреби в реальному часі. Проаналізовано інноваційні підходи до маркетингу, які допомагають підприємствам не лише привертати нових споживачів, а й створювати лояльність до бренду, що є важливим аспектом успішного розвитку в умовах непередбачуваних змін на ринку. Запропоновано визначення маркетингових інструментів – як методів, засобів та технологій, що використовуються для аналізу ринку, виявлення потреб споживачів, просування продукції та побудови довгострокових відносин із клієнтами, які охоплюють широкий спектр напрямів (від класичних інструментів, таких як реклама та прямий маркетинг, до сучасних цифрових технологій, таких як соціальні мережі, аналітика даних та автоматизація маркетингу).

Галузь застосування результатів. Маркетинг, комунікативний маркетинг, управління, реклама, ризик–менеджмент, економіка.

Висновки. Встановлено, що основні маркетингові інструменти – це динамічні комбінації платформ і сервісів (включаючи соціальні мережі, email–маркетинг, SEO), які називають сучасним цифровим маркетингом. Визначено такі базові маркетингові інструменти: Ranktracker, Sendinblue, HubSpot, Statusbrew, Google Analytics, WordPress, Slack, BuzzStream, Basecamp, Filmora, що являють собою елемент інноваційного розвитку та формування попиту в умовах невизначеності, і можуть поліпшити реалізувати маркетингові стратегії різних компаній в соціальних мережах. Доведено, що за допомогою даних інструментів можливо автоматизувати безліч процесів та оптимізувати маркетингові кампанії, що призведе до їх подальшого інноваційного розвитку та конкурентоспроможності, а також формування та збільшення попиту на продукцію компаній в умовах невизначеності та ризику.

Ключові слова: маркетингові інструменти, формування попиту, інноваційний розвиток, умови невизначеності, Ranktracker, Sendinblue, HubSpot, Statusbrew, Google Analytics, WordPress, Slack, BuzzStream, Basecamp, Filmora, управління, компанії.

Formulation of the problem. In the current environment of rapid changes in the economic environment and globalization, competition in the market is becoming increasingly intense. Businesses are forced to look for new ways to meet customer needs and increase their competitiveness by applying innovative methods and strategies. In such circumstances, marketing tools play a key role in generating demand, as they allow for more accurate monitoring of market changes, forecasting consumer behavior, and adapting offers to their new needs. Due to the uncertainty of the economic environment and changes in consumer preferences, tools such as digital marketing, social media, content marketing and personalization of offers are becoming important, allowing for effective communication with the target audi-

ence and responding to their needs in real time. In addition, innovative approaches to marketing help businesses not only attract new customers but also build brand loyalty, which is an important aspect of successful development in the face of unpredictable market changes.

Marketing tools in an uncertain environment play a key role in adapting businesses to a rapidly changing environment, helping to generate demand, taking into account changes in consumer behavior, technological progress, and global economic fluctuations.

Analysis of research and publications on the problem. The problems of marketing tools as an element of innovative development and demand generation under conditions of uncertainty have been considered by various authors in the

economic, marketing and innovation literature: Ph. Kotler, P. Drucker, V. Bagiev, V. Tarasevych, and A. Jose, whose works on marketing were devoted to strategic marketing and demand management, and who considered marketing tools as the key to the success of innovative solutions. David A. Aaker and C. M. Christensen analyzed how innovation and marketing strategies allow companies to operate successfully in the face of uncertainty. Jean-Jacques Lambin and Lynch A. R. studied the adaptation of marketing tools in conditions of instability and their role in demand generation.

The following economists are worth highlighting among domestic authors: Yu. Doroshenko, S. Shumskyi, O. Borysenko, Yu. Fisun, A. Tkachenko, O. Zhamoïda, H. Zhosan, O. Karpenko, Ye. Matviichuk, M. Kochevoi, O. Kolesnyk, H. Vlasova, I. Kulyniak, D. Holovetskyi, I. Losheniuk, O. Zeleniuk, S. Markova, O. Holovan, V. Kovalenko, H. Ostrovska, O. Ostrovskyi, O. Pashchenko, V. Vyhovskiy, T. Zavalii, D. Pedchenko, A. Proshchenko, T. Riabova, Yu. Sotnikov, A. Butenko, V. Chobitok, A. Kibets, O. Shulha and others.

However, the issues related to the high level of uncertainty, rapid technological changes and unstable market conditions (integration of innovative technologies into marketing, creating demand for innovative products under conditions of uncertainty, adaptation of marketing strategies to consumer behavioral changes, synergy of traditional and innovative approaches to marketing) still remain unresolved, which in turn requires further study of the optimal combination of traditional marketing methods with new digital and innovative tools.

Presenting main material. In the present-day world, innovations play a key role in business development. In the context of rapid digitalization and growing competition, marketing tools are becoming an important element in ensuring sustainable innovative development of enterprises, where the use of innovative marketing tools allows businesses to:

- increase the effectiveness of advertising campaigns through precise targeting;
- reduce marketing costs through process automation;
- increase competitiveness by responding quickly to changes in consumer needs;
- create new sources of revenue by introducing innovative services or products.

Thus, marketing tools are methods, tools and technologies used to analyze the market, identi-

fy consumer needs, promote products and build long-term relationships with customers, covering a wide range of areas (from classic tools such as advertising and direct marketing to modern digital technologies such as social media, data analytics and marketing automation) [2–12].

The role of marketing tools in driving innovation cannot be underestimated, as the use of Big Data, CRM systems and artificial intelligence allows companies to better understand customer needs and expectations, which helps to create innovative products and services. Tools such as Google Ads, social media (Facebook, Instagram, TikTok), SEO, and content marketing allow you to quickly test new ideas, collect feedback, and adapt your strategy. Implementation of marketing platforms such as HubSpot, Marketo, or SendPulse optimizes workflows and ensures quick response to market changes. The use of personalization tools, such as recommender systems, increases customer loyalty and promotes an innovative approach to interacting with the audience [3–9].

Examples of successful use of marketing tools for innovation include: Tesla, which actively uses social media and content marketing to promote its electric vehicles while introducing innovative approaches to production and sales; Amazon, which uses Big Data and machine learning algorithms to predict consumer needs and improve its service, including fast delivery and recommendations; Nike, which creates innovative marketing campaigns by integrating digital platforms, such as fitness apps and customized offers.

There are many marketing tools in the world that help marketers develop and generate demand in an environment of risk and uncertainty. In other words, effective marketing tools offer benefits such as understanding audience interests, creating original content, and managing social media, among others [11–16].

Let's take a look at the TOP-10 key marketing tools that will help companies innovate and generate demand in the face of uncertainty (Table 1).

1. Ranktracker is a modern digital tool for SEO management and search rankings analysis that helps improve the online presence of a business, providing extensive functionality for monitoring keywords, analyzing competitors, checking backlinks, and studying search traffic trends. The main value of Ranktracker lies in the ability to adapt the market-

Table 1. TOP-10 main marketing tools

Tool	Year of foundation	Owner	Country of origin	Area of application
Ranktracker	2005	Link-Assistant. Com	United Kingdom	The best tool for SEO
Sendinblue	2012	Sendinblue	France	The best email marketing tool
HubSpot	2006	HubSpot, Inc.	USA	Best marketing CRM
Statusbrew	2015	Statusbrew	India	Best social media management tool
Google Analytics	2005	Google LLC	USA	Best tool for analytics
WordPress	2003	Automattic	USA	Best content management tools
Slack	2013	Salesforce	USA	Best tools for marketing team collaboration
BuzzStream	2008	BuzzStream, Inc.	USA	Best marketing tools for influencers
Basecamp	2004	Basecamp, LLC	USA	Best tool for project management
Filmora	2015	Wondershare	China	Best video marketing tool

Source: based on [1–10].

ing strategy to changing market conditions, which is especially important in times of uncertainty.

Figure 1. Ranktracker – a digital tool for managing SEO

Source: based on [1–5].

Innovative development using Ranktracker allows you to collect real data on consumer demands, which is the basis for making decisions about the development of new products or services. The tool helps to identify competitors' strengths and avoid their weaknesses, which helps to create a unique market offer. Constant monitoring of positions in search engines allows you to respond quickly to market changes and adapt your promotion strategies.

Ranktracker is a key element in demand generation due to its ability to identify trends, improve brand visibility, and increase customer engagement. Ranktracker is also an effective tool for risk mitigation, as it provides up-to-date analytics that allow for informed decision-making; helps optimize marketing costs through targeting; and helps adapt strategies to new market realities by forecasting demand dynamics. Thus, Ranktracker is

not just a technical tool for SEO, but a full-fledged element of a marketing strategy that promotes innovative business development and ensures stability even in difficult conditions.

2. SendinBlue is a multifunctional marketing automation platform that helps businesses generate demand, establish communication with customers, and increase the effectiveness of advertising campaigns (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. SendinBlue is a multifunctional marketing automation platform

Source: based on [1–5].

The main functions of SendinBlue include: Email marketing, process automation, multichannel, CRM system, analytics, and reporting. SendinBlue's role in the face of uncertainty is manifested in the fact that the platform allows businesses to quickly adapt to market changes thanks to flexible tools for planning and implementing marketing strategies, while providing access to modern automation technologies that help reduce manual labor costs. Personalization of offers increases customer trust and stimulates repeat purchases, where, thanks to

the segmentation of the contact base, companies can work with individual groups of consumers, taking into account their interests and needs.

Also, in the face of uncertainty, SendinBlue’s analytical tools allow companies to predict customer needs and adapt their offers. Among the main advantages are affordability, ease of use, and wide integration capabilities (the platform can be easily integrated with other services such as CMS, CRM, or e-commerce platforms). Thus, SendinBlue is a powerful tool for marketing communications that helps businesses stay competitive in an unstable environment. Thanks to its innovative features, this platform not only helps to generate demand, but also ensures effective company development by automating and personalizing customer interactions. The best marketing CRMs today are HubSpot, Salesforce, monday.com, Zendesk Sell, Zoho, ActiveCampaign, and Nutshell.

3. HubSpot is a modern CRM platform that provides a wide range of tools for marketing automation, sales management, customer service, and analytics. The main feature of HubSpot is the integration of all processes into a single ecosystem, which allows businesses to interact more effectively with customers and adapt to rapid changes in the market (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. HubSpot – CRM platform as a single ecosystem

Source: based on [1–5].

In today’s market challenges, HubSpot is a tool that stimulates innovative business development through digital transformation, adaptability to change, and effective collaboration (the platform unites marketing, sales, and service teams, increasing their coherence and productivity). In times of instability, it is especially important to generate new demand. Thus, HubSpot allows you to: identify customer needs through data

analysis, personalize marketing, and implement inbound marketing strategies (creating valuable content to attract potential customers and develop long-term relationships) [17–21].

Thus, HubSpot is not only a marketing automation tool, but also a strategic resource that helps businesses adapt to new conditions, optimize processes, and generate demand even in the face of uncertainty. Its use allows companies to increase competitiveness and ensure sustainable development in a dynamic environment.

4. Statusbrew is a social media management tool that helps businesses communicate effectively with their audience, generate demand, and improve marketing strategies (Fig. 4). In times of uncertainty, such as economic fluctuations, social changes, or unforeseen circumstances, Statusbrew allows companies to be flexible and adaptive to new challenges. Statusbrew enables rapid customer engagement across multiple social media platforms, including automated publishing, analytics, and content management, enabling companies to innovate their marketing campaigns by simplifying content creation, management, and analysis. Statusbrew also helps marketers create adaptive strategies based on changes in consumer demand and market trends.

Figure 4. Statusbrew – a tool for social media management

Source: based on [1–5].

In times of uncertainty, when it becomes more difficult to predict the market’s reaction to changes, Statusbrew becomes an important tool for monitoring trends and consumer behavior, allowing you to respond quickly to changes, customize campaigns according to current moods and audience demand. Thanks to the tool’s analytical capabilities, marketers can anticipate changes in demand and adjust their strategies accordingly to attract new customers and maintain the loyalty of existing ones [18–23].

Thus, Statusbrew acts as an important element in building an innovative marketing process that allows

cial investments. Thus, WordPress is an effective marketing tool that allows businesses to develop innovatively, adapt to changes in demand, and be flexible in the face of uncertainty [16–22].

7. Slack is a communication and collaboration platform that is widely used to exchange information between teams, departments, and partners in companies (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. Slack – a platform for communication and collaboration, information exchange between teams, departments and partners in companies

Source: based on [1–5].

As a marketing tool, Slack is a powerful element of innovative development and demand generation in an uncertain environment due to its key capabilities: flexible communication, integration with other tools, community building and audience engagement, innovative marketing campaigns, crisis management, and collaboration on innovations. Thus, Slack is not only a platform for communication, but also a powerful tool for developing marketing strategies in an ever-changing environment, which helps to generate demand even in times of uncertainty. Some of the best influencer marketing tools are BuzzStream, HypeAuditor, Storyclash, and BuzzSumo.

8. BuzzStream is a marketing tool that allows companies to effectively communicate with influencers, bloggers and other media representatives to generate demand for their products or services. BuzzStream is used in automated processes to manage interaction with media partners, create PR campaigns, and monitor the effectiveness of such campaigns (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. BuzzStream is a marketing tool for generating demand for products or services

Source: based on [1–5].

BuzzStream helps to automate many stages of marketing campaigns, which reduces time and resources and increases efficiency. The platform provides an in-depth analysis of interaction with potential partners and target audiences, which allows you to fine-tune your promotion strategies based on consumer behavioral patterns. Using influencer marketing through BuzzStream allows companies to adapt to market changes faster, particularly in times of uncertainty, and achieve high engagement of target audiences.

During periods of economic or social instability, BuzzStream allows companies to: build flexible and adaptive strategies, use social proof, and increase audience reach. Some of the best project management tools are Basecamp, Kissflow Project, Wrike, Monday.com, ProofHub, and Clarizen. Thus, BuzzStream is an important tool for marketers, as it helps to adapt promotion strategies to uncertainty, stimulating demand and ensuring innovative development in a competitive environment.

9. Basecamp is a powerful project management and teamwork platform that allows organizations to effectively coordinate their efforts in a changing environment (Fig. 9).

Figure 9. Basecamp – a platform for project management and teamwork in a changing environment

Source: based on [1–5].

In the context of marketing tools, it can become an important element of innovative development and demand generation due to several key aspects:

Basecamp allows you to create a centralized place for organizing work where the team can track all tasks, which allows you to quickly adapt to changes in the market, respond quickly to new customer needs, and adjust marketing strategies in response to uncertainty.

Basecamp enables the marketing, sales, support, and development teams to work together on campaigns, which increases the speed of response to changing conditions.

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ТРЕТЯК В. А.

Сучасний стан та особливості державного регулювання інвестиційної діяльності сільськогосподарських підприємств в умовах воєнного стану

Предметом дослідження є теоретико–методичні аспекти визначення сучасного стану та особливостей державного регулювання інвестиційної діяльності сільськогосподарських підприємств в умовах воєнного стану.

Метою дослідження є аналіз й дослідження сучасного стану сільськогосподарських підприємств, а також визначення особливостей державного регулювання інвестиційної діяльності сільськогосподарських підприємств в умовах воєнного стану.

Методи дослідження. В статті було використано загальноекономічні методи дослідження: метод аналізу та синтезу; індукції та дедукції; групування та класифікації; метод порівняльного аналізу; таблично–графічний метод та ін.

Результати роботи. Встановлено, що з початком повномасштабного вторгнення РФ на територію України інвестиційна діяльність сільськогосподарських підприємств та її державна підтримка набуває особливої уваги через те, що саме аграрний сектор становить основу у забезпеченні продовольчої безпеки України, особливо в умовах воєнного стану. Визначено, що державна підтримка може забезпечити стимулювання інвестицій, пропонуючи фінансові механізми та допомагаючи функціонуванню сприятливого середовища для іноземних і внутрішніх інвесторів, що є критичним для розвитку сільського господарства в умовах воєнного стану. Проаналізовано індекси ціни на сільськогосподарську продукцію та виявлено, що індекси цін за 2023 р. залишаються нижчим за рівень 2022 р., коливаючись у межах від 94% до 99%. Найвищі показники продуктивності праці на підприємствах, які здійснювали сільськогосподарську діяльність показали Вінницька, Івано–Франківська, Львівська, Рівненська, Сумська, Тернопільська та Хмельницька області за